

Sustainability and Innovations Techniques in India with Special Reference to the Agriculture and Rural Development

Bimla Pandey¹ & Santosh Kumar Sharma²

1, 2 Associate Professor, Motherhood University, Roorkee
Mob.: 8909376583

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Abstract

Ability to continue existing over time is what we mean when we talk about sustainability. The term "innovation" refers to the act, process, or activity of innovating or the term "innovation" refers to anything novel, be it a process, an idea, a product, etc. This research paper illustrates how creative techniques in agricultural and rural development of our country lead to sustainable development for our country as a whole. In addition to this, the study focuses on the numerous advances that have been accomplished in the areas of agriculture and rural development. The researcher has come to the conclusion that there is a significant demand for sustainable agriculture and the development of rural areas through the implementation of appropriate innovations.

Key words: Sustainability, Innovation, Agricultural, Rural Development etc

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability means being able to live forever. The term "innovation" refers to the act, process, or activity of innovating or The term "innovation" refers to anything novel, be it a process, an idea, a product, etc. This research paper illustrates how creative techniques in agricultural and rural development of our country lead to sustainable development for our country as a whole. In addition to this, the study focuses on the numerous advances that have been accomplished in the areas of agriculture and rural development. The researcher has come to the conclusion that there is a significant demand for sustainable agriculture and the development of rural areas through the implementation of appropriate innovations.

THE OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To acquire an understanding of the ideas of Innovations and Sustainability
2. To investigate the many new approaches that have been taken in the areas of agriculture and rural development
3. To investigate the importance of rural revitalization and environmentally responsible agriculture through technological advancements.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In this study article, the secondary data provide the most important source of information for the data collecting. The study work was completed with significant use of the information that was available concerning Sustainable Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Development. The study paper could not be completed without the information that was obtained from all of the available Journals, Related books, the Web, Articles, Publish and unpublished information, and Papers.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The present research sheds insight on comprehending the notions of innovation and sustainability. No pollution of the environment will result from the implementation of straightforward advances or the production of products using natural raw resources. In the second part of this research project, we investigate a variety of recent advancements made in the fields of agriculture and rural development. Therefore, conducting this study will assist in acquiring understanding about the various forms of inventions. Thirdly, this research highlights the importance

of incorporating innovations into farming practises in order to ensure long-term sustainability. In addition to this, it highlights the fact that sustainable development is dependent on inventions that are harmless to the environment and contribute to the preservation of ecological equilibrium.

Definitions of the Term "Sustainability", "Sustainability" refers to the use of "renewable fuel sources, the reduction of carbon emissions, the protection of the environment, and a strategy for maintaining the fragile ecological balance of our world. In a nutshell, sustainability is an approach that prioritises preserving the natural environment, as well as human and ecological health, without sacrificing innovation or putting our way of life in jeopardy. The study of how natural systems function, maintain their diversity, and produce what they require to keep the ecological balance in check is what is meant when someone refers to the research as "sustainability."

Components of Long-Term Sustainability

At the World Summit on Social Development in 2005, three fundamental domains were singled out as contributing significantly to the theory and practise of sustainable development in the social sciences. These "pillars" are the following:

1. Economic Development

Especially in the developing world, economic growth is about providing people what they want without compromising the quality of life, and decreasing the financial burden as well as superfluous governmental regulations and processes of doing the right thing.

2. Social Development

Among the various components that make up this pillar, one of the most essential is raising awareness about the need for legislation to protect people's health from pollution and other actions that can be hazardous that are carried out by businesses and other groups.

3. Environmental Protection

It is necessary to take steps to safeguard the environment, such as recycling, cutting down on the amount of power we use, turning off electronic gadgets completely rather than leaving them on standby, and walking shorter distances rather than using the bus. Businesses have a responsibility to reduce pollution and minimise the amount of carbon dioxide they release into the atmosphere. There are monetary and non-monetary benefits associated with the installation of renewable energy sources in our homes and places of business. The third pillar, and for many people, the most important worry about the future of humanity, is the conservation of the environment. Ecosystems, air quality, resource integrity, and environmental stressors should all be studied and maintained, but the stressors should be the focus of our study and preservation efforts.

Principal Objectives of Sustainable Development

The United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development held a meeting in the year 2012 to discuss and develop a list of goals, including the following:

- To make efforts towards end of poverty and hunger
- To maintain better standards of education and healthcare - particularly as it pertains to water quality and better sanitation
- To achieve gender equality
- To achieve sustainable economic growth while promoting jobs and stronger economies
- All of the above and more while tackling the effects of climate change, pollution and other environmental factors that can harm people's health, livelihoods and lives.
- To achieve sustainability to include health of the land, air and sea

A. New developments in Indian agricultural practises:

Exploring Possible New Directions for Agricultural Development in India Rural livelihoods and the growth potential of the agricultural sector have been influenced by policy changes and experiments in a variety of ways. These reforms and experiments range from liberalising input markets to ensuring employment for the rural poor. One third of Indian farmers are considered to be early adopters of technology, another third of Indian farmers are considered to be slow moving adopters of technology, and the remaining one third of Indian farmers are not likely to utilise any contemporary technology at all.

Mark Kahn, who is the head of the agri-business fund Omnivore Partners, has provided us with this insightful commentary. The organisation has made investments in a number of new businesses that are working to improve life for farmers in India.

The Department of Agriculture in India reports that the rate of farm mechanisation has been slow, with only a 2% annualised growth in the decade spanning from 2001 to 2010. The industry is well aware of the pressing need for more mechanisation as well as increased levels of production. Despite the fact that it is responsible for nearly half of all jobs in India, agriculture only makes up 14% of the country's GDP.

The following is a list of important innovations that have been developed by various startup companies:

1. The Venus flytrap

Since making the switch to pest-control traps manufactured by Barrix Agro Sciences three months ago, a farmer in the Bidar district of Karnataka named Kundal Mallareddy has reduced his use of pesticide by fifty percent compared to what it was before. Pheromone-based lures are used in the traps that are manufactured by a startup company in Bangalore, India. These lures are intended to catch crop-damaging insects and flies.

2. The First Discovery

An entrepreneur named Sagar Bhansali located in Mumbai established Anulekh Agrotech. "The company markets a product known as Biosat to farmers in the states of Maharashtra and Gujarat and packages it in 50 kilogramme quantities. In order to increase the fertility of the soil and decrease reliance on synthetic fertilisers, this product is manufactured with biochar, which is a soil amendment." "The product in and of itself does not represent an innovation. It's more of a discovery than anything else. That the Amazonians were using [this] method to improve their crop yields and that they innovated on the supply chain and business model to make it more cheap for Indian farmers is what he argues. In his article, he makes both of these statements."

3. Fruits of Innovation

The mechanisation of horticulture fields in Maharashtra is being improved by the startup company Mitra, which is situated in Nashik. The company has created sprayers that may be used in pomegranate fields as well as vineyards. According to the company's creator, Devneet Bajaj, who was a principal at an agribusiness-focused private equity firm in the past, "Sprayers are used for adding hormones that promote the growth of crops," among other things. "Sprayers are used for adding hormones that help the growth of crops." In the absence of this method, farmers would have to engage in a time-consuming and labor-intensive process known as manual dipping.

4. The Management of Crops

Software developer Krishna Kumar of Bangalore established CropIn Technology Solutions, a company that provides farming businesses with various technological solutions, in the year 2010. Large food firms are now able to monitor the development of crops on farms located all across the country thanks to a new technology that consists of a cloud-based platform that can be combined with an Android mobile app.

5. Sky met

Skymet is the most comprehensive weather monitoring and agri-risk management service provider in India. According to the information provided on their website, they are the industry leaders in assessing, anticipating, and mitigating climate risk to agriculture. As a result, they are able to cut down on financial losses that are brought on by unfavourable weather conditions.

Product: Skymet's weather website, which was launched with the intention of assisting farmers, offers services such as weather forecasting, crop insurance, and agri-risk management.

6. Digital Green

Digital Green is a non-profit international development organisation that works to improve the quality of life in rural communities all over South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa by teaching farmers how to create and show short videos as a form of community engagement. The organization's primary focus is on training farmers. These videos give farmers the opportunity to record their challenges, discuss potential solutions, and display their achievements.

Products: It makes use of technology-enabled behaviour change communication that is both cost-effective and scalable.

7. Frontal Rain Technologies

The objective of the agri-tech firm based in Bangalore is to provide high technology solutions at a reasonable price for budding companies and to bring technology to distant parts of the country.

Product: What the company has to offer According to the website of the company, Rain+ is a comprehensive collection of cloud-based products that have been developed especially for businesses who are involved in the food and agriculture industries. Rain+ is able to provide assistance to enterprises at all stages along the value chain, beginning with the cultivation stage and continuing through the processing, logistics, wholesale trade, retail trade, and worldwide sales stages.

8. **Agro Star**

Agrostar, headquartered in Pune and operating as a "direct to farmer" mobile commerce platform, works hard to deliver high-quality agricultural inputs to the doorsteps of farmers.

Product: Farmers are able to get a variety of agricultural commodities through Agro Star, including seeds, crop nutrition, crop protection, and agri-hardware products. All they need to do is give a missed call to the company's 1800 number or use their mobile app to place their order. This removes the danger of products being unavailable, of products being of a lower quality than expected, of duplication, and of agricultural goods being adulterated.

B. A few forward-thinking ideas for India's rural areas

1. **Eco-Cooler:**

It has the power to reduce indoor temperatures by up to 5 degrees Celsius, which is on par with what an electric centrally installed air conditioning system is capable of doing. This cooling capacity is achieved through evaporative cooling. In certain circumstances, the Eco Cooler is capable of bringing the indoor temperature down from a blistering 86 degrees Fahrenheit (30 degrees Celsius) to a more bearable 77 degrees Fahrenheit (25C).

It is said to be the first air conditioner in the world that does not run on electricity, and the person who came up with the idea wanted to share it so that as many people as possible may benefit from it.

2. **A whirling toy (button spinner) This is a centrifuge:**

A device that employs the utilisation of the centrifugal force concept is referred to as a centrifuge. The sensation of an outwardly exerting force that is known as centrifugal force is experienced by bodies that are travelling in a circular direction.

3. **Water wheel**

Ashvin Maliya is the inventor of the water wheel, which is a cylindrical drum with a capacity of more than 45 litres. He has a Possess Learning License in farming.

The physical effort of lugging water containers can be eliminated with the use of a water wheel, which can be rolled on the ground.

Innovative Concepts for the Advancement of Rural Areas in India:

1. Utilizing the Local Resources This can be accomplished by making summertime preparations to use nearby water resources such as rivers and storage tanks, such as removing holes in the tanks, building new reservoirs and bunding up the current ones so that no water is wasted. In a similar vein, if there are any mines in the area, particularly those containing iron, coal, or granite, they ought to be mined so that the local populace can be given with work opportunities.
2. Establishment of Rural Industries All of the village industries can be categorised broadly as falling into one of the following categories:
 - a) Agro-based industries such as sugar production, jaggery production, oil processing from oil seeds, pickle production, fruit juice production, spice production, and dairy product production, etc.
 - b) Industries dependent on forests, such as the production of goods made of wood and bamboo, the production of honey and coir, and the manufacture of plates made of leaves.
3. Services: A diverse selection of services, such as repairing mobile devices and maintaining agricultural equipment, are examples of the work that falls under this category.
4. Startups are entrepreneurial endeavours that are freshly formed enterprises that strive to satisfy a need, want, or problem in the market place by building a sustainable business model centred on products, services, processes, or platforms. Startups are also known as early-stage companies. Some examples include: agriculture and its associated value chains; food and beverage manufacturing; fisheries (both culture and trade); rural microfinance; rural health care; education in rural areas; and more.
5. Services Relating to Computers and the Internet: Offering Computer Training as well as Repairing Services, Internet-based businesses such as e-commerce, ticket booking for trains and buses, and digital marketing agencies offering services such as social media marketing, email marketing, and so on.

6. Encourage entrepreneurial activity in rural areas; these businesses could be any of the following types:
 - a). Individual Entrepreneurship: This form of starting a business entails the exclusive ownership of the company.
 - b). Group Entrepreneurship: This primarily refers to forming partnerships, limited liability companies, and public limited liability companies.
 - c). Cluster Formation Entrepreneurship encompasses not-for-profit organisations, community-based organisations, small and medium-sized businesses, and even the networking of various types of organisations. These also include both formal and informal associations of a group of people that are based on factors such as caste, occupation, income, and so on.
 - d). Cooperative Entrepreneurship: This refers to an independent association of people who have joined together in business.

CONCLUSION

“The income of the people, contributing to the offer of aid to marketing and to Entrepreneurship in rural areas is extremely important to India's overall economic growth and, more specifically, to the growth of India's rural economy. It helps create jobs in rural areas with low capital, which boosts the real growth of agriculture by reducing hidden unemployment, underemployment, unemployment, poverty, migration, and economic inequality.” Additionally, it raises the “real development of agriculture by increasing the productivity of agricultural land. The programmes for rural development ought to combine the building of infrastructure, the provision of education and health services, the financing of agricultural endeavours, and the encouragement of non-agricultural activities in rural areas in which rural women and the rural populace can participate. The transformation of a developing country into a developed one can be accomplished through the promotion of rural development and entrepreneurial activity in rural areas.” The encouragement of “entrepreneurial endeavours in rural areas is of the utmost significance in the context of generating profitable employment and narrowing the growing gap between rural and urban areas.”

Monitoring “rural development programmes, supplying the appropriate information at the appropriate time, providing timely and adequate credit, and continuously motivating bankers, Panchayat union leaders, and voluntary service organisations will lead to the development of rural entrepreneurship, which will in turn lead to the development of rural areas.”

SUGGESTIONS:

1. Methods That Involve a Significant Amount of Effort Techniques that require a lot of labour should be implemented in rural industrial units because of the hidden unemployment that exists in our agricultural sector.
2. Make available “financial assistance with manageable rates of interest Rural entrepreneurs should be able to obtain funding from financial institutions like ICICI, SIDBI, IDBI, IFCI, and SFC at a low interest rate and with limited collateral security in compliance with flexible terms and circumstances.”
3. The Role of the Government “The government ought to play a role in the provision of infrastructure, warehousing facilities, and the export of the commodities produced by rural business owners to other countries.”
5. “Non-Resident Indians living in cities and rich villagers living in rural areas should help build and support rural industries.”

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